

Virtual Acoustics, Close Microphone Techniques, and Choral Blending

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1. Virtual Acoustics in Joint Performance: Perception of Room Acoustic Variations in Ensemble Performance

Introduction

The acoustic characteristics of a performance space significantly influences musicians' auditory experience, influencing the ability to interact and synchronize within an ensemble. Understanding how room acoustics affect musical performance is crucial for optimizing acoustic attributes of performance spaces, and supporting musicians in various performance settings. This study explores how changes in room acoustic conditions impact musicians' awareness and perception of their surroundings, with a particular focus on ensemble performance. To achieve this, we employ virtual acoustics, a technique that allows precise manipulation of room acoustic properties through the process of auralization. By systematically adjusting acoustic characteristics of performance space, this pilot study aims to assess musicians' sensitivity to environmental changes, determine preferred acoustic conditions, and investigate the role of acoustic feedback in performance. Through this approach, it seeks to offer insights into the perceptual and cognitive effects of varying acoustic conditions on ensemble performance and musical blending.

Virtual acoustic environments involved in this study are achieved through a process called 'auralization': when an audio signal is "processed to contain features of a simulated acoustical space" [1]. The term auralization is introduced, by analogy with visualization, to describe the process of rendering audible sound fields. Mendel Kleiner, who coined this term defines it as follows; *Auralization is the process of rendering audible, by physical or mathematical modeling, the sound field of a source in a space, in such a way as to simulate the binaural listening experience at a given position in the modeled space* [2]. Auralization involves the use of measured, synthesized, or simulated numerical data [3] to generate virtual acoustic environments. The process consists of several stages, including the capture of the sound source signal, its convolution with the Room Impulse Response (RIR), and subsequent sound field synthesis or reproduction. The RIRs, which represent the transfer function from the sound source to the receiver, detail how the acoustic environment modifies the signal as it travels from the source to the receiver.

Auralization can be used to modify the acoustic properties of an enclosed environment, enabling the tuning of acoustic features of the room to meet specific requirements. This can be achieved through real-time auralization by utilizing a loudspeaker array designed for sound field synthesis. This approach also allows for the recreation of virtual environments over multi-channel speaker systems, enabling researchers to replicate the acoustic characteristics of one space and overlay them onto another. Also referred to as active acoustics systems, the resulting combination allows for “the adjustability of the virtual environment to suit the needs of the music and the performer” [4]. These reproduction systems have the capacity to perceptually augment the sonic environment of a real-time performance, for example by making a relatively small room sound like a concert hall.

Virtual Acoustics and the MMR

Figure 1a: The MMR shown with all banners and curtains deployed to limit its reverberation time.

Figure 1b: MMR with passive absorbers lifted and/or retracted, showing custom diffusion panels installed in the space.

The Multimedia Room (MMR) is a research and performance space located in McGill University's Schulich School of Music. The space features acoustic treatment designed by the architectural acoustics firm Kirkegaard to minimize the reflections and acoustic responses of the physical room. Specially made diffusers break up sound waves as they encounter surfaces, scattering them so that they no longer have a uniform time response. Further acoustic absorption can be achieved through the deployment of banners and curtains, limiting the space's early reflections and reverberation time. Early reflections are sound waves that reach the listener shortly after the direct sound, typically within the first 50–80 milliseconds, and represent the initial interaction of sound with the room's surfaces, most notably the floor, ceiling, and walls, which help perceptually define an enclosed environment. The reverberation time is the time it takes for the sound to decay by 60 dB in an acoustic environment after the sound source has stopped. When combined with the virtual acoustics system, the room's inherent characteristics can therefore be significantly attenuated in favor of simulated spaces.

Aside from its passive acoustic treatments, the MMR is equipped with a Meyer Constellation system for active acoustics. This is a proprietary virtual acoustic system that is highly calibrated to every space in which it is installed. Because of a prolonged testing and adjustment period, the Constellation is able to create a variety of room responses in real time without the risk of feedback. As the MMR also features passive acoustic treatments, these different auralizations must take into consideration the relationship between feedback suppression and fixed passive acoustic positions in the space. Once chosen, these auralization settings can then be “tweaked” by changing the ratio of early reflections to reverb tail, adjustment of tail length, as well as the application of high and low-pass filters.

Schulich Singers and Virtual Room Perception

This preliminary experiment was conducted as part of a series of experiments on choral blend held at the MMR. Findings from this experiment were used to inform virtual acoustics decisions. We invited the Schulich Singers, a McGill University choir, to conduct a typical rehearsal in the MMR. While they rehearsed, and without their knowledge, we changed the acoustic settings of the space. The time intervals of these changes were randomized but followed a pattern of increasing reverberation tail length. We provided four different room acoustic settings, which are listed in the table below. Their corresponding reverberation times, assessed using the T30 parameter (RT60 estimated from a 30 dB sound decay), are also included in the table.

Condition A

- Constellation Setting: No Simulated Acoustics
- Description of Reverb Characteristics: No active reverb. Passive banners at 50% (more than 0.5 seconds)

Condition B

- Constellation Setting: Percussion
- Description of Reverb Characteristics: Short RT (Approximately 1.2 seconds)

Condition C

- Constellation Setting: Concert Hall
- Description of Reverb Characteristics: Second longest RT (more than 1.5 seconds)

Condition D

- Constellation Setting: Cathedral
- Description of Reverb Characteristics: Longest RT (more than 2.5 seconds)

Figure 2: The Schulich Singers in rehearsal in the MMR. An informal experiment was conducted on their perception of the room response and their preference.

As part of our investigation, we asked singers if they were aware of environmental changes during their performance. Out of 20 participants who responded to the exit survey, 10 of them

reported that they were not aware of two or more of the reverb changes, and 7 reported that they were not aware of any acoustic changes at all.

After the initial portion of the experiment, we also returned to each condition and, this time informing them of each change, had them perform a long-held note with a defined cut, and invited them to pay attention to the reverb after the note was cut. We then asked them to rank these conditions in order of preference. *Cathedral* and *No simulated acoustics* were both ranked as the second most preferred environment. It is interesting to note that these were our two extremes, as *No simulated acoustics* had the shortest reverberation time—it being the natural condition of the room—and the Constellation’s “Cathedral” preset boasts its longest reverberation time. These settings seemed to be polarizing in general among our subject pool, as they also were our least preferred (*No simulated acoustics*, at 10 participants) and second least preferred (*Cathedral*, at 7 participants) acoustic settings.

Figure 3: Acoustic settings ranked by preference and the number of subjects who gave each ranking.

Around half of our participants most preferred the system’s *Concert Hall* setting which, with a reverberation time of around 1.5 seconds, most closely resembles a mid-sized performance hall. In fact, an overwhelming majority ranked this setting within their top two, while *Percussion* had the greatest number of participants calling it second best.

The results of this preliminary study gave us the opportunity to tweak some of the Constellation factory presets before we continued with further experiments. They also showcase some of the issues we experience when conducting perception research with musicians. That half of our participants were unaware of two or more reverb changes shows that, while completing the cognitively complex tasks of singing and rehearsing, singers may not be immediately aware of uncued changes in their acoustic environments. This may have to do with the cognitive load in performance and rehearsal, but they may also experience a very high running reverberance ratio. Running reverberance is the ratio of a sound source’s direct sound against its room reflections, which we could presume would be a significant value for choir singers.

As a singer’s direct sound source is a physiological instrument located inside their body, the way they experience direct sound is quite different from instruments that are separate from and held further away from the body. For example, an electric guitarist’s guitar amplifier may be several

feet from the performer, who may hear its direct sound blended with acoustic reflections from the floor, ceiling, walls, and other surfaces. In this way, understanding the relationship between how a singer experiences both the ratio of direct to indirect sound and how it differs from other instrumentalists is critical to understanding how room acoustics affect their performance and ability to blend with other musicians.

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2. Close-Microphone Techniques for Capturing Individual Instruments in Ensemble Performances: an Acoustic and Perceptual Perspective

Introduction

Accurately capturing individual sound sources when recording a multi-musician performance requires a crucial balance between obtaining “acoustically clean” signals from each instrument and preserving musicians' visual and auditory feedback from co-performers and the room acoustic environment. This balance is crucial for research on orchestral and ensemble sound, particularly in studies on musical blending between instruments in ecological conditions, as well as applications in virtual reality orchestra simulations and music recording techniques. When it comes to individual instruments, the direct approach to capture acoustically clean signals is to record them in an anechoic environment, by electronically providing room acoustic feedback to performers if needed. On the other hand, capturing ecologically valid and acoustically clean signals of multiple instruments of an ensemble remains challenging due to the multitude of factors involved. These challenges can be addressed through three methods. (1) recording each instrument of the ensemble separately in an anechoic chamber while providing external audio and visual cues [1, 2], (2) recording each instrument individually during a joint musical performance by situating the entire ensemble or orchestra in an anechoic environment [3, 4], or (3) employing close-microphone techniques to capture individual instruments during a performance in a traditional performance setting [5].

Previous research highlights that a musician's individual performance is significantly influenced by factors such as visual and audio feedback from the co-performers [6, 7], joint performance strategies [8, 9], and the room's acoustic feedback [10, 11]. Therefore, recording the sound sources individually or as an ensemble in a reflection-free environment, even with artificial visual and auditory feedback, may not necessarily preserve the intrinsic and natural representation of the orchestral/ensemble sound. Conversely, recording individual sound sources using close-miking techniques offers a viable approach that inherits the qualities of joint performances by incorporating collaborative performance strategies, audio-visual feedback between musicians, and room acoustic feedback into the recordings. This makes it the optimal choice for musical performance research, particularly for investigating the source-level blending between instruments in realistic joint performances under in-situ acoustic conditions. However, the presence of cross-talk between sound sources due to spatial proximity, noise from the musician and instrument, and room acoustic feedback in reverberant environments are the main challenges of this method, potentially degrading the quality of individual instrument recordings. Therefore, both subjective and objective evaluation of the quality requirements of the close-microphone recordings of instruments in a joint performance is necessary to validate their applicability in musical performance research and music recording techniques. This module presents pilot experiments investigating the acoustic and perceptual quality aspects of a specific close-microphone recording technique through the recording of singers in a choir performance.

Pilot Study on the Objective and Subjective Quality of Close-mic Recordings

A preliminary investigation on the applicability of a potential close-microphone recording technique in choral singing was conducted at Hochschule für Musik Detmold. The solo and joint performances of two singers (one male and one female) from a choir were recorded at Detmold Concert House under varying acoustic conditions, using two different microphones: a studio-quality Neumann TLM 127 cardioid microphone and a Sennheiser KE4 capsule measurement microphone. While the TLM 127 microphones were positioned in front of the singers in a conventional setup, a novel method was tested with the KE4 capsule microphone, where the SPL calibrated KE4 microphone was attached above the nose tip and directed toward the mouth to explore its applicability for isolated source recording. The study explored the variations in the close-mic recording outputs with the changes in the acoustic environment surrounding the singers by adjusting the spacing of singers, incorporating acoustic panels, and modifying room acoustics using the concert house's artificial reverberation system. A total of twelve conditions were examined by systematically altering three key factors: (1) the singer-to-singer distance (1 m and 2 m), (2) the placement of absorbers (no absorbers, individual enclosures around the singers using absorbers, and absorbers placed on the floor), and (3) the reverberation time (natural RT60 of 1.6 s and an artificially extended RT60 of 3.2 s). For each acoustic condition, sound samples were recorded with the singers performing both individually and together using these two different sets of microphones, and used for the analysis.

Figure 1: Close microphone quality recording experiment at Detmold University, showing a close spacing with no barrier (top) acoustic baffling (middle) and a close-up of the nose microphone (bottom).

Sound samples were prepared from the recordings of each acoustic condition, with one singer performing (either male or female) while the other remained silent. These samples were then used to objectively analyze the mic bleed caused by the singer at the silent co-performer's microphone for both microphone techniques. The results suggest that the KE4 capsule microphone consistently exhibits lower mic bleed between the two singers compared to the Neumann TLM 127 microphones, demonstrating this reduction across varying room acoustic conditions and singer separations with at least 10 dB lower mic bleed between the KE4 capsule microphones. Analyzing the SPL calibrated KE4 capsule microphones shows that, while certain acoustic conditions shows a reduction of almost 40 dB from the singer's mic to the silent co-performer's mic, even under highly reverberant conditions with 1-meter separation distance (3.2 s RT without absorbers), they maintain almost close to 30 dB difference in sound pressure level between these capsule microphones (the audio samples for this condition are provided in the web version of this publication). This significant signal-to-noise ratio supports the applicability of these close-mic recordings.

A perceptual evaluation of the KE4 capsule microphone recordings was carried out among expert listeners with musical and technical ear training, mainly Tonmeister students at the Hochschule für Musik Detmold. They reported a high signal-to-noise ratio and satisfactory quality, along with significantly reduced cross-talk from neighboring sources. Additionally, they confirmed the recordings' quality and suitability for further mixing processes.

Experiment with the Shaar Hashomayim Synagogue Choir

As part of a series of experiments done in the Multimedia Room (MMR) at McGill University's Schulich School of Music, we applied this microphone technique to a small vocal ensemble in order to examine its efficacy in an acoustic environment with a setting closer to real performance.

The Shaar Hashomayim Synagogue Choir, a religious men's choir of twelve voices plus one soloist, participated in the experiment. Unlike the singers in the Detmold experiment, choir members would be actively listening to each other in order to blend, and we did not use any physical baffling between performers. While baffling created more isolation between singers during initial testing, this change was made to bring the experimental protocol into a more natural performance environment. The Cantor (soloist) was physically separated from the choir by 2 meters, in order to mimic their spacing were they singing in synagogue, but other choir members were seated relatively close to each other in a semi-circle opposite the conductor.

The choir was recorded using Schoeps MK4s in a spaced AB configuration, a Neumann KU100 in the center of the musicians, and the channel-based and Ambisonics setup.

Figure 2: Close microphone on the Cantor of the Shaar Hashomayim Synagogue Choir.

Figure 3: Shaar Hashomayim Choir in rehearsal.

The choir arrived to conduct their typical rehearsal, during which we experimented with different acoustic environments via the Meyer Constellation system. In the end, they chose an acoustic setting that they felt best suited their performance, and we recorded two performances of liturgical work, an example of which is provided below.

As you can hear from this excerpt from *Shema Yisrael* (see web version of this publication), some microphone signals are very isolated, while others. While some microphone signals have a completely anechoic characteristic, others also captured a neighboring voice. In the future, experiments with placement and spacing could help eliminate these issues. Despite this, there is no prevalent room characteristic or reflection in any of the signals individually. However when all anechoic sources are mixed together, a perception of space can be heard in the slight timing delays between performances.

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3. An Investigation of Choral Blending through Soundfield Capture, Acoustic Evaluation, and Perceptual Analysis Methods

Introduction

When several musicians perform together, the resulting “blend” of their sounds represents the “fusion of multiple timbres into a single timbral image” [1]. Blend is often understood as the end goal of orchestration and performance; how, and when, blend occurs, as well as how musicians go about achieving it, has been the subject of particular study [2]. This project focuses on a particular subset of ensemble blend, the “often adjudicated but seldom researched” choral blend [3]. Singers “employ a built-in neurological instrument” to varying effect when they are performing solo or in a choir [4]. Blend is at once a verb—a collective action among musicians—and a noun, the “aesthetic product” of an ensemble’s performance [5]. In addition to the direct sound musicians hear from themselves and other performers, reflected sound from the environment also functions as a strong aural feedback system. In this project we are also investigating how this feedback system affects the blending between musicians.

This investigation represents the culmination of a series of choral blend experiments conducted in the Multimedia Room (MMR) at McGill University during October 2022. In this experiment we investigated singers’ perception of choral blend, having them perform varied repertoire in several acoustic environments and ensemble spacings.

Our research questions were as follows:

1. What is the influence of room acoustics in choral blend?
2. Are there acoustic environments that singers find more “supportive” than others?
3. How do singers change their performance strategies to different acoustic environments?

Materials and Methods

In this experiment we tested three different acoustic environments which were created using a combination of the MMR’s passive acoustic banners and curtains as well as the active Meyer Constellation system: a “dry” setting with all passive acoustic systems fully deployed and no auralized outputs from the Meyer Constellation system, the “Percussion” setting which is a relatively short tail and a tweaked Early Reflection (ER) response of +1.5 dB, and the

“Cathedral” setting which has a long decay tail and was tweaked to have no ER and -2 dB on a perceptual brightness rating.

Room acoustic measurements were taken in the three environments to characterize their acoustic properties both objectively and subjectively, including Room Impulse Response (RIR) and Speech Transmission Index (STI) measurements. The RIRs were measured at multiple source-receiver locations, and the room acoustic parameters representing aspects such as perceived reverberation and clarity were extracted in accordance with the ISO standards [6]. Additionally, STI values, representing speech intelligibility, were estimated in accordance with the IEC 60268-16 standard. The three acoustic environments involved in this study exhibited distinct acoustic properties, including different reverberation time; 0.6 seconds for the ‘Dry’, 1.3 seconds for ‘Percussion’, and 1.9 seconds for the ‘Cathedral’ (these T30 values are averaged over 500-1000 Hz octave bands).

Along with these acoustic measurement techniques mentioned above, an acoustic camera was used to record the singers' performance, enabling a visual analysis of sound emission from the sources and the room reflections (see Figure 1b). This device allows for the investigation of the intensity and localization of the sound sources and room reflections for different frequency bands.

Constellation or Room Settings: Dry (Banners down and curtains closed)

- Comments/Modifications: No Simulated Acoustics
- Reverberation Time (T30): 0.6 s

Constellation or Room Settings: Percussion

- Comments/Modifications: ER +1.5 dB
- Reverberation Time (T30): 1.3 s

Constellation or Room Settings: Cathedral

- Comments/Modifications: ER -infinity, -2 dB perceptual brightness
- Reverberation Time (T30): 1.9 s

Figure 1a: The acoustic camera

Figure 1b: Screen capture of the camera recording of a performance

To capture signals with the least amount of room response, we used the experimental close microphone technique described in our other work on close microphone techniques. While this anechoic capture system is ideal for separating sound signals, we also implemented spaced and soundfield capture systems. These systems captured varying amounts of the virtual acoustic environment to serve as a comparison point for the anechoic recordings.

Figure 2: A diagram showing the main, surround, height, and soundfield capture systems in the space of the MMR. Circles represent microphones with omnidirectional polar patterns, while the doubled circles represent the dual cardioid microphones used for the back heights. Please note that this is the same capture system used in the ODESSA IV recordings, which took place concurrently

Microphone Setup

Our microphone setup was also being used for other ongoing concurrent experiments, and therefore had to be versatile. We used anechoic close mics and spot microphones on each of our five sopranos, while the virtual acoustic environment was captured through Ambisonics, binaural, and spaced techniques. A typical channel-based recording method was based around typical acoustic recording in order to capture the room proper. This included a 7.1.4 spaced microphone technique. The 7-microphone surround layer was placed at a height of 3.16 m, while the height layer was placed at 4.68 m. The primary sound image was captured by three spaced DPA 4006 microphones in the Left, Center, and Right positions. Two additional DPA 4006 made outrigger microphones captured the extreme Left and Right aspects of the room, while a final pair in the back of the room captured the surround image. The front height capture system consisted of a pair of Schemps MK2H microphones hanging from the room's ceiling grid. The MK2H capsules have more sensitivity in the high frequency spectrum than their vanilla MK2 counterparts, which is sometimes valued in a height capture. In the rear height position, a pair of Sennheiser MKH 800 Twins NX dual-capsule microphones allow for the choosing of different polar patterns in post-production, giving the engineer the opportunity to change the directivity pattern of this particular microphone position. For binaural capture, a Neumann KU100 dummy head was placed directly under the Center position of the main microphone system at around ear height. Finally, we placed two Sennheiser Ambeo first order Ambisonics microphones in high and low positions to capture the two vertical perspectives on the auditory scene. Audio was recorded in 48k/24bt to accommodate compatibility with the Zylia Higher Order Ambisonics microphone—which was not used for this particular experiment but was for other recording sessions this week—and certain spatial audio decoder systems. Session video was recorded using two angles (a left looking and right looking shot) in 4k resolution.

Experiment

Participants were asked to sing together to achieve a blended choral sound & rate how easy/difficult this was to achieve. Subjects rated on a scale of 1-10 how “Supportive” each spacing and acoustic environment felt while completing their group performance task. They were also given the opportunity to give overall impressions and comments on each acoustic environment, as well as rank the three acoustic settings in terms of overall preference, and describe which spacings they found difficult to perform in. Subjects were cycled through a combination of acoustic environments and inter-musician distances. We created a randomized combination of works and spacings within each acoustic setting in order to ensure that all pieces were performed in all spacings and acoustic settings while minimizing the interaction between variables as much as possible.

Figure 3: Subjects performing an excerpt in mid spacing and the room's dry acoustic setting (all banners and curtains fully deployed)

Distances:

- Close spacing: 0.75m between singers
- Mid spacing: 1.5m between singers
- Wide spacing: 2.5m between singers

Works:

1. Mozart, *Laudate Dominum* (soprano solo) from *Vesperae solennes de confessore* K. 339 (soprano solo), bars 11-25 [7]
2. Händel, *Lascia ch'io pianga* (soprano aria) from *Rinaldo*, bars 1-8 [8]
3. Purcell, *See We Assemble* (choir soprano) from *King Arthur*, bars 1-8 [9]

These works were chosen by project supervisors Malte Kob and Martha de Francisco as passages that could showcase a variety of musical articulation, while also being familiar enough repertoire that all singers would have a degree of familiarity with them.

Results

Singer Perception

Out of the ranked distances and acoustic settings, the singers generally found the Cathedral (longest tail) setting at a Close spacing the easiest position to blend in, and the most supportive acoustic environment. This clip of “See We Assemble” is from what is collectively their highest rated spacing, acoustic environment, and musical excerpt. (Available in web version.)

The singers rated the dry/absorptive acoustic setting at the "Mid" singer spacing lowest in terms of supportiveness. One singer referred to this setting as the most "vulnerable" in her survey feedback. This clip shows their lowest rated spacing, acoustic environment, and musical expert. (Available in web version.)

An Outlier

While overall subjects preferred the combination of Close spacing and the “Cathedral” virtual acoustic environment, one singer preferred the combination of Wide spacing and the “Dry” or most absorptive acoustic setting, ranking it highest in her overall preferences. While this was unusual given that it is the exact opposite of the group’s overall preference, she stated that she was best able to distinguish between the voices of the other participants and pay attention to minute timing differences in this position and acoustic setting. Because this participant gave her highest rating to this position, the group’s overall pick for the room setting that gave them the least amount of support became the Mid spacing instead of Wide.

Observations and Feedback

When ranking acoustic environments in terms of preference at the end of the survey, the answers from all five singers very closely followed their supportiveness ratings. At the same time, one subject expressed that the concept of finding acoustic environments “Supportive” confused her. While the researchers gave a definition that included decreasing the effort of, or bolstering her singing, this confusion ultimately was not totally resolved. This study revealed a different approach may be needed when discussing room reverberation or auralization with performers, which has become an ongoing topic of inquiry.

Changes in Methodology

Originally, our experimental design had the sopranos in a straight line, to limit sight-line variables. Our subjects however requested a semi-circular arrangement, as they considered visual cues from each other an inseparable aspect of group performance. In support of this participants, without prompting, immediately and spontaneously nominated a conductor for their group performance technique. Therefore, these visual variables cannot be separated from our results. As our study progressed, we also held a small discussion among the singers and researchers on the use of vibrato in Händel’s *Lascia ch’io pianga* aria. While typically vibrato-style singing would be appropriate for solo performance, in the end it was toned down in order to accommodate a more uniform "choral" sound. One soprano gave the feedback that she found straight-singing this piece more difficult.

Future Work

While initial results show interesting trends among singer motivations and preferences in group performance, our ongoing line of inquiry is to compare the singers' qualitative responses to quantitative signal processing analysis, as well as additional qualitative responses from listeners.

Signal Analysis

The room acoustic parameters that represent clarity, reverberation, intelligibility, etc., are being assessed for the acoustic environments involved in the study, and the sound samples of individual singers singing the same musical piece in those specific acoustic environments are extracted. Spectral, temporal and loudness-based, musically oriented signal features (e.g. Spectral centroid, formant position & strength, onset & offset time, etc.) will be extracted from the sound samples, and their correlation with the acoustic parameters will be investigated to see how the acoustic environment influences the performance of individual singers in achieving a blended sound.

Listener Analysis

Initial results from this study suggest that singers feeling acoustically supported may not directly translate to an improved musical performance, as their highest rated spacing and acoustic environment may not have been the best technical performance of the musical excerpt. We plan to conduct testing using a Multiple Stimuli with Hidden Reference and Anchor (MUSHRA) or similar expert-based evaluation methodology to examine this relationship. Additionally, to examine if and how capture systems influence the listener perception of choral blend, we will ask for ratings of various capture systems (from anechoic to soundfield) placed within the room along its reverb continuum. Results will be compared to objective reverb attributes extracted from the signal processing analysis to examine whether there is consistency in the perception of blend, and what objective factors with which this impression might relate.

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